

SEARCH FOR NEW ANTISPASMODICS. PART I

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In search for new antispasmodics, some pyrazolone derivatives containing tertiary bases have been synthesised.

During recent years a number of synthetic compounds have been discovered, which exhibit antispasmodic activity. Many of these products are much simpler in structure than the naturally occurring antispasmodics, papaverine and atropine. Diethylaminoethyl esters of diphenylacetic acid and analogous compounds have been found to possess powerful antispasmodic activity (cf. Blicke, *Ann. Rev. Biochem.*, 1944, 13, 549). Relatively simple piperidine derivatives are also known to have antispasmodic activity (Cerkovnikov and Prelog, *Ber.*, 1941, 74 1648; Fellows and Cunningham, *Federation Proc.*, 1942, 1, 151; Lee and Freudenberg, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1944, 9, 537; Foster, Moench and Clark, *J. Pharm. Exp. Therap.*, 1946, 87, 73; Kwartler and Lucas, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 2582). Thus, it appears that all the efficient antispasmodics, although differing widely in molecular structure, are, in general, salts of tertiary bases. In view of the interesting observation of Notkin and Webster (*Rev. Canadian Biol.*, 1942, 1, 660) that amidopyrine, which is a pyrazolone derivative, possesses antispasmodic activity, it has been considered desirable to introduce tertiary bases into a pyrazolone molecule and to have the resulting products examined for any spasmolytic activity.

Ketones containing an active methyl or methylene group have been shown by Mannich (*Ber.*, 1920, 53, 1368; 1922, 55, 356; *Arch. Pharm.*, 1926, 264, 741; 1927, 265, 589) to condense with formaldehyde and secondary bases. 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-acetylpyrazolone (Stolz, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1897, ii, 55, 154) has now been condensed with formaldehyde and secondary bases to yield compounds of the type (I). Compounds other than ketones, but containing an active methyl or methylene group, may sometimes be induced to respond to Mannich reaction (cf. Kermack and Muir, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 3089). As 1-phenyl-3-methylpyrazolone contains a reactive methylene group (cf. Narang *et al.*, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 427), this compound has been substituted for the ketone in the Mannich reaction to furnish, when allowed to react with formaldehyde and secondary bases, compounds of the type (II).

[where R is piperidino, dimethylamino or diethylamino group]. The maximum yields of the above types of compounds (I and II) attained were of the order of 55-60%, rendered possible by using 1 mol. of 1-phenyl-3-methylpyrazolone or of its 4-acetyl derivative, 1.5 mols. of formaldehyde and 1.5 mols. of the secondary base (cf. Kermack and Muir, *loc. cit.*), the

formaldehyde being in the form of commercial 40% formalin. These compounds (I and II) are amphoteric, being readily soluble in cold dilute alkali (cf. Ghosh and Das Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 63) and yielding *hydrochlorides* (which are practically insoluble in water) and *methiodides*. The acidic property is evidently due to the presence of the mobile hydrogen atom in the 4-position.

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The methods of preparation of the compounds (I and II) are essentially the same in all cases. The general method of procedure followed is therefore given below in case of one particular preparation.

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-(β-piperidinopropionyl)-pyrazolone (I, R=piperidino).—A mixture of 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-acetylpyrazolone (21.6 g.), formaldehyde (11.3 c.c., 40%), piperidine (12.8 g.) and hydrochloric acid (18 c.c., 20% w/v) in alcohol (120 c.c.) was heated on the water-bath for about 6 hours. Next day the solution was diluted with water, when a pasty solid was precipitated. It was dissolved in cold dilute alkali and extracted with benzene and then with ether to remove the pasty matter as far as possible. The alkaline solution was stirred with charcoal for about 1 hour, filtered and just acidified with acetic acid, when a solid was precipitated. It was crystallised from ethyl alcohol-ethyl acetate (1:1) in colorless, rectangular plates (yield 58%), melting at 220-21° to an orange-yellow viscous liquid. (Found: N, 13.27. $C_{18}H_{23}O_2N_3$ requires N, 13.41 per cent). It is readily soluble in cold dilute alkali and gives a red coloration with alcoholic neutral ferric chloride.

The *hydrochloride*, which was obtained by adding the requisite quantity of hydrochloric acid to an alcoholic solution of the base, was crystallised from dilute alcohol in colorless, rectangular plates, m.p. 250-52°. (Found: Cl, 9.58. $C_{18}H_{24}O_2N_3Cl$ requires Cl, 10.17 per cent). The *methiodide*, which was prepared in nitrobenzene solution, was crystallised from absolute alcohol in colorless needles, melting at 266-67° to a dark red liquid. (Found: I, 27.18. $C_{19}H_{25}O_2N_3I$ requires I, 27.91 per cent). The *phenylhydrazone* was crystallised from alcohol (in which it is sparingly soluble) in colorless, rectangular plates, m.p. above 300°. (Found: N, 16.98. $C_{24}H_{29}ON_5$ requires N, 17.37 per cent). It is readily soluble in cold dilute alkali

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-(β-diethylaminopropionyl)-pyrazolone (I, R=diethylamino) was crystallised from ethyl alcohol-ethyl acetate in colorless, rectangular plates, m.p. 212-13°, yield 60%. (Found: N, 13.61. $C_{17}H_{23}O_2N_3$ requires N, 13.95 per cent). The *hydrochloride* melts at 254-55°. The *methiodide* melts at 268-69°. (Found: I, 27.98. $C_{18}H_{25}O_2N_3I$ requires I, 28.66 per cent). The *phenylhydrazone* does not melt even at 300°. (Found: N, 17.52. $C_{23}H_{29}ON_5$ requires N, 17.90 per cent).

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-(β-dimethylaminopropionyl)-pyrazolone (I, R=dimethylamino) was crystallised from ethyl alcohol-ethyl acetate in colorless, rectangular plates, m.p. 220°, yield 58%. (Found: N, 15.02. $C_{15}H_{19}O_2N_3$ requires N, 15.38 per cent). *Hydrochloride*, m.p. 252°. *Methiodide*, m.p. 275-76° (Found: I, 29.94. $C_{16}H_{23}O_2N_3I$ requires I, 30.60 per cent).

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-piperidinomethyl-pyrazolone (II, R = piperidino) was crystallised from alcohol in colorless, rectangular plates, m.p. 224-25°, yield 55%. (Found: N, 15.82. $C_{16}H_{21}ON_3$ requires N, 15.5 per cent). *Hydrochloride*, m.p. 251-52° (Found: Cl, 11.02.

$C_{16}H_{22}ON_3Cl$ requires Cl, 11.56 per cent). *Methiodide*, m.p. 279-80° (Found : I. 30.36. $C_{17}H_{24}O_3NI$ requires I, 30.75 per cent).

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-diethylaminomethyl-pyrazolone (II, R=diethylamino) was crystallised from alcohol in colorless, rectangular plates m.p. 221-22°. (Found : N, 15.87. $C_{15}H_{21}ON_3$ requires N, 16.21 per cent). *Hydrochloride*, m.p. 255-56°. *Methiodide*, m.p. 270-271° (Found : I, 30.98. $C_{18}H_{24}ON_3I$ requires I, 31.67 per cent).

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-dimethylaminomethyl-pyrazolone (II, R=dimethylamino) was crystallised from alcohol in colorless, rectangular plates, m.p. 221-22°, yield 57%. (Found : N 18.34. $C_{13}H_{17}ON_3$ requires N, 18.18 per cent). *Hydrochloride*, m.p. 253-254°.

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